

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Connecting complex and simplified models of tipping elements: a nonlinear two-forcing emulator for the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation

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Abstract

Background

Despite its far-reaching implications, accurately characterizing the tipping dynamics of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) remains a significant challenge. Complex models, including Earth System Models (ESMs) and Earth System Models of Intermediate Complexity (EMICs), offer valuable insights; however, they are computationally expensive and subject to substantial uncertainties in identifying AMOC tipping points. In contrast, simple conceptual models based on non-linear dynamics have been developed to represent tipping elements such as the AMOC. These models can be calibrated against complex models to explore various scenarios and forcing spaces, functioning as emulators. Traditionally, such emulators have focused on a single forcing variable, typically global mean temperature, despite the well-established influence of freshwater fluxes on AMOC dynamics. Moreover, existing two-forcing AMOC emulators lack robust calibration methods against complex models.

Methods

In this study, we develop and validate a two-forcing AMOC emulator that incorporates global mean temperature and freshwater flux, grounded in non-linear dynamics. The emulator is calibrated against

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the AMOC response within the EMIC cGENIE. After validation, the emulator is integrated into SURFER, a reduced-complexity climate model, enabling rapid simulation of AMOC trajectories under diverse emission scenarios.

Results

By considering Greenland Ice Sheet melt, the emulator captures two additional collapses and one overshoot without tipping trajectories for emission scenarios ranging from SSP3-7.0 to SSP5-8.5. Furthermore, the emulator allows the assessment of the critical forcing manifold of the AMOC in the complex model, enabling the identification of combined forcing thresholds for the AMOC and serving as a tool for comparing the sensitivities of complex models.

Conclusions

With its low computational cost and calibration accuracy, our tool represents a significant advancement in exploring AMOC dynamics in future climatic scenarios. Finally, the methodology used to develop this emulator is generalizable, providing a framework for studying other tipping elements in research.

Plain language summary

As global temperatures rise due to greenhouse gas emissions, certain key components of the Earth's climate system are approaching critical thresholds known as tipping points, beyond which significant changes may occur. One such tipping element is the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC), a crucial ocean current responsible for redistributing heat between the hemispheres. If the AMOC were to collapse, it could result in substantial regional changes in temperature, precipitation, and other critical aspects of the climate. However, the exact location of the AMOC tipping point and the time it would take to collapse remain uncertain due to limitations in complex climate models. Additionally, running these complex models is computationally expensive, making it difficult to explore a wide range of potential future scenarios. In this study, we developed an emulator—a simplified conceptual model calibrated using a complex model—to reproduce the behaviour of the AMOC during a potential collapse. This emulator is built on a new methodology that improves the alignment between simplified dynamics and complex models. The resulting tool enables the production of numerous AMOC simulations under various emission scenarios with low computational cost, while remaining consistent with our understanding of the physical processes that govern the AMOC. For example, this new emulator simulates AMOC collapse under future high emission pathways. This emulator and methods enable researchers to better explore the potential responses of the AMOC to future emissions and strengthen our ability to predict and prepare for abrupt changes in the climate system.

Keywords

Climate change, Tipping Points, AMOC, Emulator, Non-linear dynamics, SURFER, cGENIE.

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1. Introduction

1.1 The AMOC as a tipping element: Addressing high uncertainties

The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) is a key component of the climate system. It plays a central role in the transport of heat and salt throughout the global ocean and significantly influences both regional and global climate dynamics¹⁻³. The AMOC has been identified as a tipping element, a large-scale component of the climate system that can reach a tipping point⁴. A tipping point refers to a critical threshold in a forcing parameter, known as the bifurcation parameter, beyond which a small perturbation of this parameter can cause the tipping element to transition from one equilibrium state to another, resulting in a significant qualitative change⁴. For the AMOC, the secondary stable equilibrium corresponds to a collapse state, where the circulation ceases⁵. A cessation or even a slowdown of the AMOC would have significant consequences for temperatures in the North Atlantic³⁻⁶, as well as impacts on the carbon cycle⁷, monsoons², and, potentially, other tipping elements^{5,8,9}.

Effectively simulating the AMOC requires an understanding of its physical dynamics. The AMOC operates through the sinking of large amounts of warm, salty water from the South Atlantic into the North Atlantic. As this water cools, it becomes sufficiently dense to sink into the depths, forming the North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW), which then returns to the South Atlantic^{10,11}. The AMOC is a component of what is referred to as the thermohaline circulation, as it is driven by density differences determined by the temperature and salinity of the water. The tipping point of the AMOC corresponds to a critical threshold in the stratification of Atlantic waters. With global warming, the increase in Atlantic water temperature reduces its density, thereby enhancing its buoyancy¹². This thermal forcing is the dominant mechanism driving AMOC weakening¹³⁻¹⁵. The second forcing mechanism involves a disturbance in the salinity of the water within the Atlantic. As the Greenland Ice Sheet (GIS) melts due to global warming, large quantities of freshwater are added to the deep-water sinking regions in the North Atlantic. This freshwater flux reduces the water's density, increasing its buoyancy and diminishing its ability to sink into the depths, thereby weakening the intensity of the AMOC¹⁶⁻¹⁸. On the other hand, future variations in water salinity in the North Atlantic may result from changes in the precipitation-evaporation (P-E) balance driven by temperature anomalies¹⁹. Consequently, there exists a critical threshold of water stratification that, if exceeded for a prolonged period, can become self-sustaining, as the AMOC can no longer transport warm and salty water to the North Atlantic²⁰, ultimately leading to the collapse of the circulation^{5,16,21}. Once reached, this collapse state is irreversible, as returning to the critical value of the bifurcation parameter will not allow the system to return to its initial equilibrium. A characteristic hysteresis phenomenon is thus present, preventing a return to the initial state within timescales relevant to human lifetimes^{4,22}.

There is evidence that the AMOC has slowed during the 20th century²³, with reconstructions indicating a 15% decline

over the past 70 years²⁴, bringing it closer to its tipping point. However, observations of AMOC slowdown are subject to considerable uncertainty¹⁰, and although the AMOC may have collapsed in the past^{8,25,26}, accurately forecasting its future evolution—when and at what rate it may collapse remains a significant challenge^{5,27,28}. Estimates of the tipping point for the AMOC must therefore rely on models, but the results vary significantly²⁸. Some studies place it at a global mean temperature anomaly of 8°C, while others suggest it may already be as low as 1.4°C²⁹. Consequently, some studies estimate that a complete collapse of the AMOC could occur by the end of this century³⁰, or not until 2300¹⁶. In addition, there is also sensitivity to the rate of the applied forcing^{31,32}. Lastly, the tipping dynamics of the AMOC cannot be fully understood without considering those of the GIS, which has a melting threshold beyond which its decline becomes irreversible³³. In addition to the destabilizing effect of GIS melting on the AMOC due to freshwater input, a collapse of the AMOC would, conversely, have a stabilizing effect on the GIS. Indeed, the resulting regional cooling following an AMOC shutdown would slow down the melting of the GIS. Thus, a coupling between the AMOC and the GIS exists, potentially giving rise to tipping cascades³⁴, where the collapse of one system triggers the failure of another or, conversely, helps stabilize it³⁵. However, significant uncertainties remain in the projections of these dynamics⁵.

1.2 The need for simplified models capturing first-order dynamics

This significant uncertainty regarding the future evolution of AMOC collapse stems from the diversity of models and approaches employed. To assess the stability of the AMOC and the associated thresholds, stability diagrams are constructed using hysteresis experiments, in which the forcing is slowly varied along a back-and-forth scenario. However, due to their prohibitive computational demands, complex models, such as Earth System Models (ESMs) are unable to simulate numerous complete AMOC hysteresis curves³⁶. Consequently, Earth System Models of Intermediate Complexity (EMICs) offer the best compromise between explicitly resolving processes and computational efficiency for generating AMOC hysteresis curves^{27,37}. However, even EMICs exhibit significant variability in the location of the tipping point, and consequently, in their projections of the future evolution of the AMOC²⁷. Moreover, due to their significant computational costs compared to simpler models, these complex models are not well-suited for efficiently exploring the range of potential forcing scenarios and their associated AMOC responses. Additionally, there is evidence that the current generation of complex climate models exhibits excessive stability due to biases in ocean salinity distribution^{38,39}. Consequently, recent studies have increasingly relied on conceptual models to simulate the AMOC and other tipping elements^{35,40-42}.

This approach primarily relies on modelling the dynamics of tipping elements through a double-fold bifurcation structure⁴⁰⁻⁴³, as stability indicators and observational analyses have shown that the AMOC resides in a bi-stable regime⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶. In this framework, the system possesses two stable equilibria

separated by an unstable equilibrium. When the bifurcation parameter reaches the critical value of the tipping point, the system can transition from its initial stable equilibrium to the second. These models mathematically impose that the AMOC behaves as a nonlinear dynamical system with this specific double-fold structure, thereby defining its intrinsic tipping element dynamics. The primary advantage of these models, beyond their ability to capture the suspected dynamical behaviour, is their computational efficiency. By calibrating these simplified dynamics using experiments from complex models, these models enable the creation of tipping element emulators. When these tipping element emulators are coupled with a reduced-complexity climate model, they offer a tool that is both process-based and computationally efficient. This enables the study of tipping element evolution in multi-millennial simulations under realistic emissions scenarios⁴⁰.

1.3 Challenges in designing a two-forcing emulator

An emulator based on the concept of a double-fold bifurcation was introduced by Martinez Montero *et al.*⁴⁷ in the reduced-complexity climate model SURFER v2.0 to simulate the dynamics of ice sheets. This emulator considers only a single forcing variable, specifically the temperature anomaly computed from emission scenarios. In SURFER v3.0, Couplet *et al.*^{40,48} developed a generalization of this emulator, allowing for the coupling of tipping elements and hence the inclusion of an additional forcing variable. The challenge, however, lies in establishing a calibration technique for the model parameters based on existing literature and complex models. In their study, Couplet *et al.*⁴⁰ employed a Monte Carlo sampling method within the parameter space of their simplified models to reproduce the configurations considered plausible in the literature regarding the state of tipping elements. In contrast to Couplet *et al.*⁴⁰, our approach focuses on calibrating the parameters of a two-parameter physical forcing emulator to align with any given hysteresis curve from a complex model. This methodology enables a more realistic calibration of the emulator while facilitating the systematic exploration of the forcing space across different emission scenarios over extended timescales. Importantly, it preserves the key characteristics of the emulated complex model, allowing for computationally efficient yet physically consistent simulations.

To our knowledge, no simplified tipping element model with two forcing parameters, capable of being calibrated using experiments from complex models, has been developed. However, the AMOC is influenced by two forcing variables: temperature anomaly and freshwater flux. Given the necessity of more realistically constraining potential future AMOC trajectories, this study seeks to address the following objective: develop an AMOC emulator with two forcing parameters — temperature and freshwater flux — that can be calibrated against hysteresis from complex models and integrated into a climate model. The paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we introduce the AMOC Tipping Calibration Module (ATCM), a simplified nonlinear dynamical model based on the double-fold bifurcation structure with two forcing parameters: temperature anomaly and freshwater flux. We also describe the calibration module used to fit the double-fold structure to any

hysteresis curve derived from a complex model. This novel module is based on the assumption of independent forcing calibration experiments, which allows for a generalization of the method by Martinez Monteiro *et al.*⁴⁷. In Section 3, we apply this calibration process to cGENIE, an EMIC, using two calibration experiments. We then validate the ATCM as an emulator by comparing its results with those of one additional cGENIE experiment. Subsequently, we integrate the ATCM into the SURFER climate model, creating a new configuration that provides a calibrated emulator of the AMOC within a fast climate model. This setup enables the analysis of overshoot without tipping phenomena. Furthermore, it facilitates further investigations into the potential collapse dynamics of the AMOC under realistic emission scenarios, utilizing the critical manifold of the complex model's sensitivity, which can be captured by the emulator. Section 4 presents an analysis of our key findings, comparing them with previous studies. It also discusses the limitations of our approach in emulating a complex dynamic using a conceptual non-linear dynamics model and outlines potential improvements to this methodology, as well as its application to emulate other tipping elements. Finally, we conclude in Section 5.

2. Methods

We introduce the AMOC Tipping Calibration Module (ATCM), an emulator designed to represent the dynamics of the AMOC tipping element with two forcing parameters: temperature and freshwater flux. The key feature of this emulator is its ability to calibrate simplified AMOC dynamics to match any hysteresis curve derived from a more complex, process-based model. We detail the equations that define the model and describe the methodology used for its calibration. The AMOC model is based on the normal form of a double-fold bifurcation, which has been demonstrated in previous studies to be effective in modelling the tipping element behaviour of the AMOC^{40,42}. The calibration technique builds upon the ice sheet emulator implemented in SURFER v2.0⁴⁷, incorporating the assumption of independent forcing in the calibration experiments. Subsequently, in the results section, the ATCM is calibrated on the cGENIE model, enabling it to act as an emulator for the AMOC.

2.1 AMOC dynamical model

The overall scheme of the ATCM is depicted in Figure 1. Given that one of the primary freshwater flux forcings of the AMOC is GIS melting, and that we aim to develop a framework that can subsequently be used to study tipping cascade phenomena, we also provide an explicit mathematical formulation of the GIS model. The non linear ordinary differential equations that describes the AMOC intensity and the GIS volume are written as,

$$\frac{d\Psi}{dt}(\Psi, T, F_{GIS}) = \left(\underbrace{-\Psi^3 + a_1\Psi^2 + b_1\Psi + c_1}_{\text{internal dynamics}} + \underbrace{d_1T + e_{12}F_{GIS}}_{\text{forcings}} \right) \mu_{\Psi}(\Psi), \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dV}{dt}(V, T, \Psi) = \left(\underbrace{-V^3 + a_2V^2 + b_2V + c_2}_{\text{internal dynamics}} + \underbrace{d_2T + e_{21}(1 - \Psi)}_{\text{forcings}} \right) \mu_V(V). \quad (2)$$

Figure 1. Schematic of the AMOC Tipping Calibration Module (ATCM). The module requires input in the form of bifurcation coordinates derived from complex experiments. These coordinates are used to adjust the calibration coefficients within the simplified tipping element model.

These equations are derived from the normal form of a double-fold bifurcation, enabling the representation of the first-order tipping dynamics of the AMOC and the GIS. Consequently, the tipping element model acts as a generic dynamical system designed to function as an emulator. The use of a generalized normal form of a double-fold bifurcation has already been demonstrated to be effective for tipping element models^{40,42,47}. The state variables Ψ and V are dimensionless variables and span the interval $[0,1]$, defining the state of the AMOC and the GIS respectively compared to their pre-industrial state. For the AMOC, Ψ is the ratio of its current intensity in S_V with its pre-industrial value while for the GIS, V is the ratio between the ice volume and its pre-industrial value. The first group of terms in Equation 1 and Equation 2 represents the internal dynamics of the tipping element. Since it is a cubic polynomial of the state variable it allows the tipping element to have 1,2 or 3 stable states depending on its forcings⁴⁰. The coefficients $a_i, b_j, c_i, d_i, e_{ij} (i,j = 1,2, i \neq j)$ do not correspond immediately to specific physical properties, but by setting these parameters, one can reproduce the stability structure diagnosed in more complex models.

The first forcing term, T , which appears in Equation (1) and Equation (2) represents the global mean surface air temperature anomaly relative to pre-industrial levels. In Equation (1), this term encapsulates the physical effects of warming on AMOC water stratification, as well as freshwater anomalies resulting from simulated P-E in the complex model. In Equation (2) the T forcing term represents the impact of temperature on ice melting in the GIS. In Equation (1), the second forcing term, F_{GIS} , represents the freshwater flux resulting from GIS melting, which weakens the intensity of the AMOC.

The parameterization of F_{GIS} is based on that of Couplet *et al.*⁴⁰ and is defined as follow:

$$F_{GIS} = \alpha_{GIS} \frac{dV}{dt}. \quad (3)$$

The freshwater contribution of the GIS is proportional to the temporal variation of its dimensionless volume. The parameter α_{GIS} relates the temporal variation of the dimensionless fraction of the GIS to a freshwater flux. The details of the computation and the value of α_{GIS} are given in Couplet *et al.*⁴⁰. Through this parameterization of F_{GIS} , we establish a dynamic dependence of the AMOC on the state of the GIS that is useful for studying tipping cascade interactions between the AMOC and the GIS, as in Couplet *et al.*⁴⁰. Finally, a collapse of the AMOC will stabilize the melting of the GIS due to its regional cooling⁵. In Equation (2) the second forcing variable Ψ is the state of the AMOC. By using a parameterization $(1 - \Psi)$ this ensures that the stabilizing effect of the AMOC on the GIS is maximum when the AMOC has collapsed ($\Psi = 0$).

The functions $\mu_\Psi(\Psi)$ and $\mu_V(V)$ are inverse time scales that describe the intrinsic dynamics of the tipping elements³². Denoting either of the two state variables as x , these functions are defined as follows,

$$\mu_x(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\tau_x^+} & \text{if } \frac{dx}{dt} > 0 \text{ and } 0 < x < 1, \\ \frac{1}{\tau_x^-} & \text{if } \frac{dx}{dt} < 0 \text{ and } 0 < x < 1, \\ 0 & \text{if } x \leq 0 \text{ or } x \geq 1. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

We define two distinct time scales for the dynamics of the tipping elements to represent the asymmetry inherent in processes associated with the GIS, as ice melting typically occurs more rapidly than ice formation. τ_x^+ represents the characteristic timescale of the intrinsic dynamics of the element transitioning from its collapsed state to its nominal state, whereas τ_x^- represents the characteristic timescale for the reverse transition, from the nominal state to the collapsed state. Here, we refer to the nominal state as the one with an active configuration of the AMOC. The third case in Equation (4) ensures that the normalized state of the tipping element, x , remains between the value $x = 0$ for the completely collapsed state and $x = 1$ indicating the initial pre-industrial state. The internal timescale dynamics are important for the evolution of tipping elements, and accurately estimating these parameters is challenging^{5,29}. In the results section, we calibrate τ_Ψ^+ and τ_Ψ^- based on a tuning procedure to reproduce the internal timescale dynamics of the AMOC in cGENIE. For the GIS, we set $\tau_V^+ = 5500$ years and $\tau_V^- = 700$ years, based on reasonable values given in the reviews by Armstrong McKay *et al.*²⁹ and Couplet *et al.*⁴⁰.

2.2 Calibration module

Now, we aim to develop a calibration algorithm that, based on the critical coordinates of bifurcation points obtained from hysteresis experiments of complex models, will calibrate the parameters $a_p, b_p, c_p, d_p, e_{ij}$ ($i, j = 1, 2, i \neq j$). We focus on validating the calibration methods for the AMOC. However, the translation to any simplified model based on the normal form of a bifurcation, such as Equations (1, 2), which include two forcings, will be reasonably straightforward. For instance, the translation for the GIS calibration is provided in the Supplementary Materials (see Data Availability). For the calibration, we seek to find the best fit for our double-fold structure to the complex hysteresis, ensuring that our simplified dynamics pass through the bifurcation points identified in the process-based hysteresis. In the paper describing the SURFER v2.0 model, Martinez-Montero *et al.*⁴⁷ develop a mathematical framework that allows, in the case of the Antarctic and Greenland ice sheet - also modelled by a canonical double-fold normal form - to be calibrated on experiments with more complex models by using the coordinates of the bifurcation points. From an epistemological standpoint, the significant advantage of the Martinez-Monteiro *et al.*⁴⁷ method is that it provides a clear link between the physically based tipping points coordinates and the calibration parameters. With this approach, the parameters are redefined such as to transparently describe the stability diagram. This method also allows to test the underlying hypothesis that the leading-order dynamics of tipping elements such as the AMOC can be captured by a double-fold. For these reasons, we aim to adhere to the calibration framework proposed by Martinez-Monteiro *et al.*⁴⁷. However, the mathematical framework presented by Martinez-Monteiro *et al.*⁴⁷ for modelling each individual ice sheet relies on a single ordinary differential equation with only one forcing parameter, namely the temperature anomaly. In our case, for the AMOC, we have two forcing parameters: the temperature anomaly and the freshwater flux.

To generalize the method of Martinez-Monteiro *et al.*⁴⁷ we need an operational assumption. Specifically, we assume that the complex models used to calibrate the hysteresis of the AMOC allow for independent application of forcing to the AMOC. In other words, if we take our ATCM model for the AMOC (see Equation (1)), we should be able to access process-based models that can force the AMOC solely through temperature anomaly while keeping the freshwater flux forcing constant, and vice versa. This is technically feasible with most models. If the aim is also to emulate the transition from the collapsed state to the nominal state, an additional constraint arises in the selection of complex models. Specifically, the complex models must be capable of conducting hysteresis experiments, which involve simulations where the tipping element remains in quasi-equilibrium. For instance, in the cGENIE experiments used for calibration of collapse dynamics, simulations span over 20,000 years (see Supplementary Materials in data availability). This requirement implies that models categorized as EMICs are generally suitable targets for emulation, as these models can perform simulations over extensive timescales while maintaining physical consistency³⁶. Throughout the text, we will refer to EMICs as the “complex” models we aim to emulate, although the emulator can be calibrated using any process-based model of the AMOC.

The recipe for our calibration, which is generalizable to N forcings, is as follows. To calibrate the coupling parameters associated with the N forcing variables, we perform N independent sensitivity experiments to independently calibrate the associated bifurcation diagrams by systematically reducing the calibration to a Martinez-Monteiro *et al.*⁴⁷-type model with only one forcing variable, as the other $N - 1$ variables become constants. For the AMOC, *EXPA* is defined as the calibration experiment of the AMOC intensity with respect to a temperature forcing, conducted using any complex model that satisfies the aforementioned conditions. From this experiment we can retrieve the coordinates of the bifurcation points denoted by,

$$(\Psi^+, T^+), (\Psi^-, T^-). \quad (5)$$

In this context, Ψ^\pm represents the normalized values of the AMOC intensity, where the system transitions from its nominal stable equilibrium state (Ψ^+) to its collapsed equilibrium state, and from the collapsed equilibrium state (Ψ^-) back to the nominal equilibrium state. The T^\pm values denote the critical temperature anomaly forcing at which the two preceding bifurcations occur within the system. The Equation (1) in the *EXPA* experiment can be written as,

$$\frac{d\Psi}{dt} = \left(-\Psi^3 + a_1\Psi^2 + b_1\Psi + c_1 + d_1T + e_{12}F_{GIS}^A \right) \mu_\Psi(\Psi), \quad (6)$$

where F_{GIS}^A represents the arbitrary constant value of the freshwater flux forcing applied during the simulation in the complex model. Consequently, $c_1 + e_{12}F_{GIS}^A$ is a constant term in this experiment, effectively reducing the conceptual model to a single-forcing experiment. This simplification enables the

application of the calibration technique proposed by Martinez Montero *et al.*⁴⁷ to determine the parameters.

$$a_1 = \frac{3(\Psi^- + \Psi^+)}{2} \quad (7)$$

$$b_1 = -3\Psi^-\Psi^+ \quad (8)$$

$$c_1 = \frac{T_{\Psi^+}^+\Psi^{-2}(\Psi^- - 3\Psi^+) - T_{\Psi^-}^-\Psi^{+2}(\Psi^+ - 3\Psi^-)}{2(T_{\Psi^-}^- - T_{\Psi^+}^+)} - e_{12}F_{GIS}^A \quad (9)$$

$$d_1 = -\frac{(\Psi^+ - \Psi^-)^3}{2(T_{\Psi^+}^+ - T_{\Psi^-}^-)} \quad (10)$$

We define *EXPB* as the second calibration experiment examining the AMOC intensity response to freshwater forcing, using the same complex model. In this experiment, the freshwater flux parameterization in the complex model is implemented as a hosing tipping experiment. This freshwater flux could originate from Greenland Ice Sheet melt or precipitation-evaporation anomalies. From this experiment, we can extract the coordinates of the bifurcation points,

$$(\Psi^+, F_{GIS}^+), (\Psi^-, F_{GIS}^-). \quad (11)$$

F_{GIS} represents the critical values of the freshwater flux forcing at which the bifurcation of the AMOC occurs. By defining T^B as the constant value of the temperature anomaly imposed during the complex model experiment, Equation (1) can be expressed as:

$$\frac{d\Psi}{dt} = (-\Psi^3 + a_1\Psi^2 + b_1\Psi + c_1 + d_1T^B + e_{12}F_{GIS})\mu_{\Psi}(\Psi). \quad (12)$$

Here, $c_1 + d_1T^B$ represents the constant term, and the method proposed by Martinez Monteiro *et al.*⁴⁷ enables the determination of two new values for the following parameters,

$$c_1 = \frac{F_{GIS}^+\Psi^{-2}(\Psi^- - 3\Psi^+) - F_{GIS}^-\Psi^{+2}(\Psi^+ - 3\Psi^-)}{2(F_{GIS}^- - F_{GIS}^+)} - d_1T^B, \quad (13)$$

$$e_{12} = \frac{(\Psi^+ - \Psi^-)^3}{2(F_{GIS}^+ - F_{GIS}^-)}, \quad (14)$$

Thus, based on the five unknowns ($a_1, b_1, c_1, d_1, e_{12}$), independent calibration experiments allows us to apply the methodological framework of Martinez Monteiro *et al.*⁴⁷ to a single forcing variable. This results in six equations with an over-determination of the independent parameter c_1 . The application of this method to calibrate the GIS model, Equation (2), is provided in the Supplementary Materials (data availability). For the GIS case, it requires a complex model capable of simulating its volume projections with independent forcing possibilities for the AMOC and temperature.

With this methodological framework, it is also possible to generalize the approach to include more than two forcing

parameters. For instance, as demonstrated in the Supplementary (Data availability), an additional freshwater flux forcing term was incorporated into Equation (1) to calibrate the impact of variations in the evaporation-precipitation balance over the Atlantic basin under future scenarios. Mathematically, the generalization to N forcing variables results in obtaining $4N - 2(N - 1)$ equations with $4 + (N - 1)$ knowns, leading to $N - 1$ over-determined equations. As will be shown in the next section with the emulation of cGENIE, these over-determinations reflect the fact that the coefficient c_1 is the shared constant across all calibrations of different sensitivity experiments. It represents the component of the model that must adjust for each sensitivity experiment while remaining consistent across all of them. What value, then, should be assigned to c_1 ? Sensitivity experiments have shown that defining $c_1 = c_1^A$, where c_1^A is determined from Equation (9), yields the most accurate results for emulating the evolution of the AMOC based on complex models. This is because temperature forcing is the primary driver of AMOC collapse¹⁵, as demonstrated, for instance, in CMIP5 experiments¹³. Consequently, we prioritize achieving the best possible calibration for temperature forcing while allowing for a greater margin of error in the calibration of freshwater flux forcing. Therefore, we adopt the value of c_1 as determined by the temperature sensitivity calibration experiment.

The final parameter in the ATCM module that needs to be calibrated is the nominal internal dynamic time scale of the AMOC, denoted as τ_{Ψ}^{\pm} . Based on Armstrong McKay *et al.*²⁹ we assume that the internal dynamic time scale of the AMOC from its nominal stable state to its collapse stable state is the same, i.e., $\tau \equiv \tau_{\Psi}^+ = \tau_{\Psi}^-$. To calibrate this parameter, the proposed experimental setup involves running a simulation with the complex model to be emulated, using a stepwise parametrized forcing of the freshwater flux while maintaining a fixed temperature forcing. For instance, the simulation, with a forcing duration of 2000 years to reach equilibrium, can start with a 0 Sv forcing. It then increases the forcing by 0.05 Sv to slow down the AMOC, decreases the forcing by 0.05 Sv until the value reaches -0.05 Sv, and repeats this procedure several times. The goal is to obtain a time series of the AMOC intensity with several instances where the AMOC is being reduced. Based on these experimental data, a manual tuning of τ within ATCM allows for determining the best value to replicate the characteristic time scale of AMOC dynamics in the complex model.

3. Results

In this section, we calibrate the ATCM using cGENIE, through three calibration experiments labelled *EXPA*, *EXPB*, and *EXPC*. The first two experiments are used to calibrate the coefficients $a_1, b_1, c_1, d_1, e_{12}$ while *EXPC* is employed to calibrate the parameter τ . Second, we validate the effectiveness of the ATCM by simulating an AMOC trajectory under a forcing configuration different from the calibration experiments and comparing the results with the original cGENIE simulation. Finally, we integrate the ATCM into SURFER to demonstrate the

emulator's capability to rapidly simulate the evolution of the AMOC while sampling the forcing space under numerous realistic emission scenarios.

3.1 Calibration with cGENIE

To validate the emulator, we applied the ATCM to cGENIE⁴⁹, an EMIC³⁷ that has already demonstrated its ability to simulate AMOC hysteresis^{14,50}. cGENIE includes an ocean circulation model (3D), a dynamic-thermodynamic sea ice model (2D) and an atmospheric energy moisture balance model (2D). The ocean model accounts for the horizontal and vertical transport of heat, salinity and biogeochemical tracers. The circulation is simulated through advection, convection, and mixing^{50,51}. cGENIE has a very simple atmospheric model, which results in a minimal effect of net changes in the Precipitation-Evaporation (P-E) balance over the North Atlantic due to global warming. However, if the ATCM is applied to emulate complex models that account for variations in the P-E balance, these would be captured in the calibration through the temperature anomaly. Following the experimental framework outlined in the Methods section, we conducted two independent sensitivity calibration experiments on the AMOC intensity using cGENIE.

The first experiment, labelled *EXPA*, consist of a 20,000-year simulation with a prescribed CO_2 forcing designed to generate a global atmospheric mean temperature anomaly. The forcing is parameterized as a linear function, increasing from 280 ppm

to 2,800 ppm. Through the internal dynamics of cGENIE, this forcing is translated into a global mean surface air temperature anomaly, starting from $T = 10^\circ C$ for the initial thousands of years and reaching $T = 10^\circ C$ after 20,000 years (Figure S1- See underlying data). This setup enables us to cover the plausible range of the AMOC tipping point location in terms of temperature forcing^{5,29} while ensuring near-equilibrium conditions for the AMOC.

The second independent sensitivity calibration experiment, labelled *EXPA*, involves a 20,000-year hosing simulation with freshwater flux forcing linearly increasing from 0 Sv to 0.2 Sv (Figure S2- See underlying data). These values are chosen to align with the plausible range of AMOC tipping point locations related to freshwater forcing^{18,27} and to be sufficient to trigger an AMOC collapse in cGENIE. The total salinity of the oceans is maintained constant in the simulation by applying a compensatory freshwater flux over the Pacific. The freshwater hosing is applied between $20^\circ N$ and $50^\circ N$ across the full width of the Atlantic (Figure S3- See underlying data) to reproduce the hosing region by Rahmstorf *et al.*²⁷. The durations of the *EXPA* and *EXPB* simulations are chosen to ensure that the AMOC is forced sufficiently slowly, allowing it to remain in near a stable state throughout the calibration experiment.

The two trajectories of the AMOC intensity obtained with cGENIE in the *EXPA* and *EXPB* experiments are shown in

Figure 2. Bifurcation diagrams of cGENIE and ATCM in the (T, F_{GIS}) forcing space. The two simulations produced by cGENIE during the calibration experiments *EXPA* and *EXPB* are shown in their respective planes as solid black lines. The identification of the bifurcation points based on these collapsed branches is marked in red, while the simplified hysteresis produced by the ATCM is shown in blue. The branch of the unstable equilibrium, which separates the two stable equilibria, is represented by the orange dashed line.

Figure 2. Since the primary objective of the ATCM is to accurately calibrate the collapse branch, we focus exclusively on simulating collapse scenarios with cGENIE. This allows to extend the duration of the simulations with the complex model and thus, obtain an AMOC as close as possible to its equilibrium in the complex model. In other words, a complete hysteresis cycle was not performed to refine our calibration of the collapse branch, but this does not undermine the validity of the results.

As demonstrated in Laridon⁵², the ATCM can also successfully emulate the AMOC trajectory of the complex model through the second bifurcation point. However, to achieve an optimal fit for the collapse trajectory, slight deviations from the bifurcation point coordinates provided by the complex model may improve the emulator's accuracy in representing the collapse trajectory. To calibrate the ATCM at the second bifurcation point (see Supplementary Materials in data availability), we therefore use the calibration simulation data from cGENIE provided in Laridon⁵².

The coordinates of the bifurcation points are extracted from the experiments and are listed in Table 1. There is no established method for determining the coordinates of bifurcation points when analysing the hysteresis of a complex model. Consequently, the selection must rely on expert judgment and a thorough understanding of the complex model's behaviour. In the ATCM model, the points Ψ^\pm for bifurcation must be the same, whether they are reached via temperature forcing or freshwater forcing. Moreover, we aim to find the best fit for temperature forcing, so we define $\Psi^\pm \equiv \Psi_{EXPA}^\pm$. Using these values, we compute the parameters $(a_1, b_1, c_1, d_1, e_{12})$, according to Equation (7–10, 14), and the results are presented in Table 2. Based on the calibration of these parameters, the simplified hysteresis loop emulated by the ATCM is shown in Figure 2. Since we calibrated the ATCM using the c_1 value from EXPA, the double-fold structure correctly passes exactly through the

two bifurcation points identified on the cGENIE hysteresis curve from the temperature forcing calibration experiment. However, this is not the case for EXPB, as will be explained in the Discussion section. Indeed, there is a $0.002Sv$ difference between the F_{GIS}^+ tipping point identified from cGENIE and the value computed by the ATCM, resulting in a relative difference between the two of 2.53%. Overall, the collapse dynamics demonstrate a reasonably good calibration against the cGENIE simulations.

The final parameter to calibrate in the ATCM to emulate cGENIE is the parameter τ , which represents the nominal timescale of the intrinsic dynamics of the AMOC. We apply the experimental protocol described in the Methods section, conducting a calibration experiment labelled EXPC with cGENIE. In this experiment, a step-by-step parameterized forcing of the freshwater flux is applied (see Figure 3b).

By doing so, the AMOC is modified to diagnose the time required to transition between equilibrium states under the applied forcing. In Figure 3a, the trajectory of the AMOC simulated by cGENIE is shown in black, while the trajectory simulated by the ATCM is shown in blue. The goal is to calibrate the parameter τ to reproduce the time lag between the intensity of the AMOC and its corresponding equilibrium intensity under the applied forcing. After calibration, a reasonable trajectory of the ATCM compared to cGENIE is achieved with a value of $\tau = 140 \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

Differences emerge at the various plateaus between the ATCM and cGENIE because the AMOC in cGENIE has not yet fully stabilized to its equilibrium state, and because more complex dynamics are incorporated in cGENIE. Additionally, the difference in the initial equilibrium state of the AMOC between cGENIE and the ATCM arises from discrepancies in the preindustrial AMOC intensity values in cGENIE and the ATCM (see Figure 2). These discrepancies will be discussed in the

Table 1. Bifurcation coordinates. The values are retrieved from the cGENIE calibration sensitivity experiments EXPA and EXPB shown in Figure 2. The F_{GIS}^- value is retrieved from cGENIE hysteresis (see Supplementary Materials in data availability). The T^- value was adjusted to improve the calibration of the upper branch.

	Ψ^+ [Adim]	Ψ^- [Adim]	T^+ [°C]	T^- [°C]	F_{GIS}^+ [Sv]	F_{GIS}^- [Sv]
EXPA	0.545	0.022	5.93	3	/	/
EXPB	0.545	0.022	/	/	0.075	0.037

Table 2. Internal dynamics parameter.

The parameters are computed with the ATCM using Equation (7–10,14) using coordinates of the bifurcation points given by Table 1.

a_1	b_1	c_1	d_1	e_{12}
0.851	-0.036	0.074	-0.024	-1.882

Figure 3. (a) Normalized AMOC intensity in the ATCM (blue) and cGENIE (black) under varying freshwater flux forcing. (b) Parameterization of freshwater flux forcing in the calibration experiment *EXPC*.

following section. Nevertheless, they do not compromise the calibration of the parameter τ , as it is designed to replicate the temporal lag between the AMOC intensity at a given moment and its corresponding equilibrium intensity during the four forcing level transitions in *EXPC*.

3.2 Validation of the emulator

To validate the emulator, we compare the ability of the ATCM to simulate the behaviour of the AMOC in cGENIE using a new experiment, referred to as *val_exp_1*. This experiment represents a combination of forcing conditions distinct from those used in the calibration experiments. The *val_exp_1* simulation spans 20,000 years and combines the thermal forcing from *EXPA* — a linear increase in CO_2 concentration from 280 ppm to 2,800 ppm (see Figure S1- See underlying data) — with a linear freshwater forcing increase from 0Sv to 0.2Sv (see Figures S2 and S3- underlying data).

The trajectories of the normalized AMOC intensity in both the emulator and the complex model are shown in Figure (4). The ATCM, despite its simplified dynamics, captures the trajectory described by cGENIE reasonably well, particularly

during the first 3,000 years of the simulation. However, after 3,000 years, a sudden drop in AMOC intensity, followed by a partial recovery, is not captured by the ATCM. This discrepancy ultimately leads to a notable difference of 26% in the AMOC intensity after 3200 years. However, the parameters of the ATCM have been calibrated to replicate the moment of complete collapse in the AMOC intensity as given by the complex model, and we observe a difference of less than 5 years between cGENIE and the ATCM. As previously highlighted, the abrupt decrease in AMOC intensity in the ATCM during the early centuries of the simulation is due to differences in the equilibrium state associated with zero temperature forcing between the ATCM and cGENIE, which result from the calibration process.

3.3 ATCM integration within the SURFER climate model

We now introduce the ATCM emulator into the reduced-complexity climate model SURFER (see Figure 5). SURFER features a process-based carbon cycle capable of reliably simulating atmospheric CO_2 concentrations and global mean temperature changes. This reduced-complexity model also simulates sea-level rise and various ocean acidification

Figure 4. Trajectories of the AMOC in the ATCM emulator (blue) and cGENIE (black) in the *val_exp_1* validation experiment with combined global mean temperature and Greenland Ice Sheet freshwater forcing.

Figure 5. Conceptual diagram of SURFER, including interacting tipping elements and their feedback on climate. Figure reproduced with permission from Couplet *et al.*⁴⁰. The ATCM is integrated into the ‘Tipping Elements’ box of SURFER.

metrics in response to anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions, while enabling simulations over timescales ranging from decades to millions of years^{47,48}. Version 3.0 of SURFER comprises 17 differential equations that describe carbon exchanges among six reservoirs: the atmosphere, terrestrial systems, upper, intermediate, and deep ocean layers, and deep-sea sediments⁴⁸. Additionally, it models temperature anomalies across ocean layers, ice sheet volumes for Greenland and Antarctica, and sea-level changes due to glacier dynamics.

SURFER has proven effective for integrating tipping element dynamics into climate simulations, as by Couplet *et al.*⁴⁰. At the time of this project, version 3.0 of SURFER was not yet available. Therefore, we chose to integrate the ATCM into a preliminary version of v3.0 (see Data Availability) which we here refer to as pre3.0. There are no major differences between versions pre3.0 and 3.0; notably, the changes pertain to the parameterization of SURFER’s carbon cycle, which is not central to this study’s objective of constructing an AMOC

emulator coupled to a reduced-complexity climate model. To integrate the ATCM into SURFER pre3.0, we decided to deactivate all components associated with tipping elements other than the AMOC and GIS.

Incorporating the ATCM emulator into a reduced-complexity climate model like SURFER provides a robust tool for examining a broad phase space and a wide range of realistic emission scenarios. This approach maintains realistic parameterizations while ensuring computational efficiency and manageable runtime. Figure 5 illustrates the fifteen full-span emission scenarios selected as inputs to simulate the evolution of the AMOC within the emulator once integrated into SURFER. These 15 scenarios represent cumulative carbon emissions ranging from 1000 to 5000 PgC into the atmosphere from 1750 to 2500, covering the spectrum from SSP1-2.6 to SSP5-8.5. After 2500 AD, greenhouse gas emissions are set to zero for the remainder of the simulations in all scenarios.

3.4 Critical manifold and sampling the forcing space

Based on the calibration of the ATCM to cGENIE, we can represent (see Figure 6) the two calibration experiments, *EXPA* and *EXPB*, as well as the validation experiment *val_exp_1*, in the forcing variable space (T, F_{GIS}) . This representation demonstrates the use of the emulator as a tool for mapping the forcing space of a given complex model. The critical manifold W_c is defined by the ATCM as follows,

$$W_c(T) = \frac{d_1}{e_{12}}(T^+ - T). \tag{15}$$

This manifold delineates the forcing space into two regions: one where the linear combinations of the variables T and F_{GIS} do not lead to a tipping of the AMOC in the emulator, and another where such combinations would eventually cause the AMOC to tip into an alternative equilibrium state. Despite the

approximations inherent in the calibration process, the ATCM provides a valuable pre-diagnostic tool for analysing forcing combinations that, if sustained for a sufficient duration³¹, are expected to lead to a complete tipping of the AMOC.

As an application, we studied the response of the ATCM once integrated into SURFER under 15 different emission scenarios spanning SSP1-2.6 to SSP5-8.5 (see Figure 7). Figure 8 illustrates the trajectories of these 10 000-year simulations in the forcing space (T, F_{GIS}) . The critical manifold W_c is the same as in Figure 5, obtained from the ATCM through the two calibration experiments *EXPA* and *EXPB* conducted with cGENIE. We observe that for 8 out of the 15 trajectories, the linear combination of the two forcing variables exceeds the bifurcation threshold of the AMOC. However, for four of these trajectories, the intensity and duration of this exceedance are sufficiently low to result in the overshoot-without-tipping phenomenon identified by Ritchie *et al.*³¹. Moreover, hysteresis phenomena are observed, as the four simulations with the highest greenhouse gas emissions that cause the collapse of the AMOC fail to restore its circulation, even when forcing levels return below critical thresholds. Finally, Figure 6 and Figure 8 highlight the importance of considering two forcing variables in the case of the AMOC, as the inclusion of freshwater flux as a forcing variable significantly lowers the temperature-associated tipping point due to their combined effects.

3.5 New collapse trajectories captured by the emulator

To demonstrate the importance of developing an AMOC emulator that accounts for both temperature and freshwater flux forcing associated with GIS melting, we compared the AMOC evolution predicted by the ATCM in SURFER with the case where the freshwater flux forcing is intentionally disabled. 15 greenhouse gas emission scenarios are used, spanning total emissions from 3000 PgC to 4000 PgC. This places their emission

Figure 6. Representation of the different forcings applied in the two calibration experiments, *EXPA*, *EXPB* and the *val_exp_1* validation experiment. The tipping points identified in the two calibration experiments are represented by the blue and red points. The red dashed line, W_c , defines the critical bifurcation manifold in the ATCM. The “Safe Zone” in the forcing space corresponds to the set of linear combinations of the two forcing variables that do not reach the bifurcation point in the ATCM. The “Tipping Zone” exceeds this bifurcation point.

Figure 7. Fifteen full-span emission scenarios, covering the emission space from SSP1-2.6 to SSP5-8.5, are used in SURFER. These scenarios account for cumulative emissions from 1000 to 5000 PgC into the atmosphere since 1750. The emission trajectories range from blue for scenarios with the lowest emissions to red for scenarios with the highest greenhouse gas emissions.

Figure 8. Representation of the 15 emission scenarios spanning SSP1-2.6 to SSP5-8.5 (see Figure S4- See underlying data) in the (T, F_{GIS}) forcing space. Their associated temperature anomaly and freshwater flux contributions are given by SURFER. The dots indicate the state of the AMOC at the end of the 10 000-year simulation. A green dot signifies $\Psi > \Psi^*$ corresponding to an active AMOC state, while a red dot indicates $\Psi < 0.1$, representing the collapsed state. The red dashed line, W_c , denotes the critical bifurcation manifold in the ATCM. The “Safe Zone” in the forcing space corresponds to the set of linear combinations of the two forcing variables that remain below the bifurcation threshold identified in the ATCM. Conversely, the “Tipping Zone” represents conditions that exceed this threshold.

peaks between those of the SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios (Figure 9).

In the case where the forcing by freshwater flux from GIS melting is deactivated (see Figure 10a), the 15 trajectories do not lead to an AMOC collapse during these 10,000-year simulations. However, overshoot without tipping phenomena are observed for the three highest emission scenarios, as the AMOC is subjected to a global mean temperature anomaly exceeding its tipping point identified at $T^* = 5.93$ °C. When the forcing with F_{GIS} is activated and calibrated with cGENIE, as developed in this paper, we observe (see Figure 10b) that for the two highest emission scenarios (3928.57 PgC and 4000 PgC), the AMOC collapses. One new additional overshoot without tipping trajectory (3642.86 PgC) is also observed. Thus, new dynamics with substantial impacts have been captured through the

development of an emulator that accounts for both freshwater flux forcing from GIS melting and temperature forcing.

4. Discussion

The objective was to develop an AMOC emulator based on double-fold dynamics incorporating two forcing variables—globally averaged temperature and freshwater flux—that could be effectively calibrated using complex models. To achieve this, we generalized the calibration method of Martinez Monteiro *et al.*⁴⁷ by assuming the feasibility of conducting independent forcing experiments for calibration.

The resulting AMOC Tipping Calibration Module (ATCM) has proven highly effective, as demonstrated in the Results section and Figure 2. It successfully adjusts its simplified double-fold structure to closely replicate the cGENIE complex model

Figure 9. Fifteen mid-range emission scenarios, spanning SSP3-7.0 to SSP5-8.5, are used in SURFER to study the interaction of temperature and freshwater flux forcings. These scenarios account for cumulative emissions from 3000 to 4000 PgC into the atmosphere since 1750. The emission trajectories range from light blue for scenarios with the lowest emissions to dark red for scenarios with the highest greenhouse gas emissions.

Figure 10. Trajectories of the AMOC in the temperature bifurcation diagram with the freshwater flux forcing deactivated Figure 10a and activated Figure 10b. The simulations run for 10,000 years. The cGENIE-calibrated double-fold dynamics of the equilibrium are represented by the black line. The trajectories simulated by SURFER are shown in colors corresponding to total emission scenarios ranging from 3000 PgC to 4000 PgC (see Figure 9).

simulations. In the calibration based on cGENIE experiments, the differences between the tipping points associated with F_{GS} obtained from cGENIE and those simulated by the ATCM are minimal. Specifically, this difference of $0.002Sv$, equivalent to a 2.5% error, falls within a reasonable uncertainty range reported in the literature^{26,28}. To calibrate the characteristic timescale parameter τ , an effective experimental design with the complex model was demonstrated.

The differences between the ATCM and cGENIE data in the calibration experiments can be attributed to two primary factors: the inherent limitations of the conceptual approach and constraints within the ATCM calibration module. The first is the inherent limitations of the simplified approach in fitting a double-fold structure to a complex hysteresis. These first limitations were known a priori. From a technical perspective, fitting a third-order polynomial to a complex curve is expected

to result in a potentially significant discrepancy between the approximation and the reality described by the complex model. The challenge, therefore, lies in identifying the most effective method to minimize this inherent error as much as possible. Here, we explain the origins of these approximations and the measures taken to mitigate them.

Technically, the first source of error in the calibration module arises from the values of the independent term c_1 , which must take the same value across all sensitivity experiments. As outlined in the Methods section, the coefficient is over-determined across the two sensitivity experiments. Consequently, a specific value of c_1 is selected based on one calibration experiment, but this value may not apply to the other. This approach implies that our simplified model is precisely calibrated to the bifurcation points of one calibration experiment (temperature forcing) but not the other (freshwater flux forcing). However,

the decision to minimize error for temperature forcing is justified because this forcing is the dominant factor influencing the AMOC^{13,14,53}.

A second limitation of the ATCM calibration module is its inability to accurately align with the pre-industrial value of the AMOC. In their single-forcing parameter model, Martinez Montero *et al.*⁴⁷ were able to mathematically constrain the calibration model such that, under zero temperature anomaly forcing, the initial state of the simplified model corresponded precisely to the pre-industrial value of the tipping element. However, this approach cannot be generalized to models with two forcing parameters, as implementing such a constraint would introduce additional restrictions on the constant forcing values F_{GIS}^A and T_B , thereby limiting experimental flexibility. However, although the difference between the actual equilibrium state of AMOC intensity during the pre-industrial period and that reproduced by the ATCM is significant (10%), it does not substantially affect the emulator's relevance. This is because, under forcings such as those associated with climate change, the system initially evolves out of equilibrium. Moreover, since the nominal timescale parameter τ has been calibrated based on cGENIE, the ATCM effectively replicates the initial trajectory of the AMOC under forcing, as shown in Figure 4.

Once the simplified dynamics of the AMOC were calibrated, the emulator was tested on a new experiment combining both forcing variables. The emulator successfully replicated the dynamics of cGENIE up to the point where physical processes not accounted for by the ATCM caused significant deviations in the AMOC's collapse dynamics relative to cGENIE. Consequently, these simplifications in the emulator's dynamics led to a notable discrepancy of 26% in the intensity of the AMOC at a specific point in its collapse trajectory. However, the primary value of constructing tipping element emulators, such as the present case for the AMOC, lies in their ability to assess, at low computational cost and with fidelity to more complex models, the predicted timing of the tipping element's total collapse. In this regard, the comparison between the ATCM and the *val_exp_1* experiment from cGENIE demonstrates that only a difference of a few years separates the prediction of the complex model from that of the emulator. Over a 20,000-year simulation, this highlights the robustness of the ATCM.

Therefore, we argue that the resulting emulator, which utilizes independent forcing experiments from complex models to calibrate tipping elements characterized by a double-fold bifurcation and two forcing variables, is relevant. The calibration produced provides a tool that is sufficiently close to the reality of the complex model being emulated to be usable as an emulator. However, complex models, whether EMICs or even ESMs, still carry significant uncertainty regarding the exact location of the AMOC tipping points and, consequently, the timing of their collapse^{5,29,53}. In this context, the ATCM should not be regarded as a tool for delivering precise quantitative projections. While it is highly likely that the model values deviate from exact accuracy, we demonstrate that they are sufficiently well calibrated to remain plausible. This is the key requirement for an AMOC tipping element emulator, enabling improved studies of the AMOC state under likely positions in

its forcing space. As demonstrated in the Results section (see Figure 7), the ATCM facilitates realistic sampling of the forcing space once integrated into a reduced-complexity climate model like SURFER. Where complex models face significant computational constraints, the presented emulator enables a large number of simulations to be performed at a much lower cost while maintaining consistency with more complex models. These computationally-efficient simulations also allow for the study of overshoot without tipping scenarios³¹ by sampling the bivariate forcing space with higher resolution (Figure 8).

Moreover, the emulator allows assessing, under the assumption that the two forcings add linearly, the critical manifold W_c of the emulated complex model. Comparing these critical varieties provides a method for assessing the inherent sensitivities of each model to AMOC collapse. A promising direction for future research would be to calibrate the ATCM using an ensemble of EMICs and possibly ESMs, allowing for the exploration of both the forcing space and the structural model uncertainty space. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that incorporating freshwater flux forcing from GIS melting into the AMOC emulator is crucial, as it allows for the capture of two new collapse and one overshoot without tipping scenarios that could not previously be modelled with temperature forcing alone. The two emission scenarios that now lead to AMOC collapse in the emulator have emission peaks falling between those of the reference scenarios SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5. This underscores the urgent need to reduce greenhouse gas emissions to prevent triggering tipping points such as AMOC collapse, in addition to mitigating baseline global warming.

Lastly, the calibration method presented here can be further generalized to include additional forcing variables (see Supplementary in data availability). Another promising avenue is applying the ATCM methodology to the Greenland Ice Sheet (GIS) (see Supplementary Materials in data availability), creating a non-linear dynamics tool calibrated on complex models to explore possible cascading collapses between the AMOC and GIS^{32,34}. Beyond the GIS, this approach to constructing tipping element emulators can be extended to other tipping elements, beginning with the six additional elements whose initial parameterizations are included in SURFER v3.0⁴⁰. Moreover, this emulator could be integrated into other reduced-complexity climate models, such as FAIR⁵⁴, with minimal technical difficulty, as it requires only the global mean temperature anomaly and a parameterization of the GIS freshwater flux as input variables from the climate model.

5. Conclusion

We have presented the AMOC Tipping Calibration Module (ATCM), an emulator of the AMOC tipping element dynamics based on a double-fold structure that, for the first time, incorporates two forcing variables that can be calibrated using experiments from complex models. To address this challenge, we adopted the methodological hypothesis that independent calibration experiments for each forcing variable could be conducted using the complex system. It was demonstrated that the constructed emulator satisfactorily reproduces the AMOC behaviour observed in the target complex model. Of course, the emulator is constrained by its simplified dynamics, which introduce noticeable differences between its outputs and those

of the emulated complex model, cGENIE. Nevertheless, the ATCM is capable of reproducing the timing of the total AMOC collapse predicted by the complex model with an error of less than five years. This result falls within the uncertainty range reported in the literature for complex models, ensuring that the emulator's outputs remain both plausible and consistent with those of the complex model. Furthermore, by accounting for both globally averaged temperature anomalies and freshwater fluxes associated with Greenland Ice Sheet (GIS) melting, the emulator effectively incorporates this key dynamic in AMOC collapse. It has thus been demonstrated that the emulator can capture two new AMOC collapse trajectories and one overshoot trajectory without tipping for emission scenarios with peaks between those of SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5. These trajectories could not be reproduced using temperature forcing alone. In addition, the ATCM offers significant computational advantages, characterized by much shorter runtimes compared to complex models. When integrated into a reduced-complexity climate model such as SURFER, the ATCM enables rapid yet realistic exploration of the forcing space under various emission scenarios. This emulator also facilitates a retrieval technique for extracting the critical manifold of the complex model within the forcing space. It provides a valuable framework for investigating boundary cases of overshoot without tipping in complex models and for comparing their sensitivities to AMOC collapse, thereby enabling the exploration of structural model uncertainty.

Finally, the calibration methodology presented here can be readily extended to other tipping elements. A promising next step would be to calibrate a GIS emulator in a similar manner, creating a tool capable of modelling cascading collapses between the AMOC and GIS when calibrated on a complex model. The methodology behind the emulator could also be applied to other tipping elements within SURFER or other reduced-complexity climate models. Therefore, beyond the tool itself, this study has developed and validated a calibration method for simplified two-forcing tipping element dynamics based on complex models, such as EMICs and ESMs. This work establishes a framework for bridging the gap between conceptual and complex models, advancing our understanding of future tipping element dynamics. It also underscores the urgent need for immediate and robust mitigation policies to address the risks associated with the potential collapse of these critical systems.

Ethics and consent

Ethics and consent were not required.

Data availability

Laridon A *et al.* 2025. Supplementary Materials. Connecting complex and simplified models of tipping elements: a nonlinear two-forcing emulator for the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation. Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14979157>⁵⁵

This repository contains the supplementary materials referred in this paper (i) GIS calibration (ii) parameterization of the AMOC with three forcing variables (iii) more details on the

cGENIE experiments used for calibration (iv) cGENIE hysteresis used for calibration of the second tipping point.

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Software availability

Laridon, A *et al.* 2025. Connecting complex and simplified models of tipping elements: a nonlinear two-forcing emulator for the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation. Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944240>

This repository contains the data as well as the scripts, the SURFER model and the ATCM used in this study. The *ATCM.ipynb* Jupyter Notebook contains the Python code where the ATCM is defined, calibrated, and validated using cGENIE simulations. The *SURFER_pre3.0_ATCM.ipynb* Jupyter Notebook contains the integration of the ATCM into the SURFER pre3.0 climate model. These two notebooks were used to generate all the figures presented in this paper. The emission scenario data required to run the simulations implemented in SURFER can be found in the *data/SURFER/* directory within the

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The code for the version of the 'muffin' release of the cGENIE Earth system model used in this paper, is tagged as v0.9.61, and is assigned a DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15021902>. Configuration files for the specific experiments presented in the paper can be found in the directory: *genie-userconfigs/PUBS/published/Laridon_et_al_2025*. Details of the experiments, plus the command line needed to run each one, are given in the *readme.txt* file in that directory. All other configuration files and boundary conditions are provided as part of the code release.

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A manual detailing code installation, basic model configuration, tutorials covering various aspects of model configuration, experimental design, and output, plus the processing of results, is assigned a DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13377225>.

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Author contributions

AL, VC, and MC conceptualized the study and its objectives, which are based on AL's MSc thesis. AL and VC are responsible for the design of the ATCM methodology. AL conducted the formal and technical analysis of the project. MC and WT managed and coordinated the research activity planning and execution. MC, as the supervisor of AL's MSc thesis and co-supervisor of AL's PhD, and WT, as the supervisor of AL's PhD, provided oversight and guidance. JG assisted in designing the calibration experiments with cGENIE and conducted them. AL analysed, with the help of JG these simulations. AL integrated the cGENIE simulations into the ATCM. AL is responsible for the study's visualization, creation, and presentation of the published work. AL wrote the original draft, produced all the figures and led the manuscript writing process. AL, MC, JG, VC and WT reviewed and revised it.

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Dipti Hingmire

University of Victoria, Victoria, British Columbia, Canada

Complex systems like AMOC require computationally expensive complex Earth System models to be run to understand its tipping points. Here the authors have developed a nonlinear two forcing emulator for AMOC and it calibrated with reduced complexity climate models. New insights regarding AMOC collapse from SSP3-7.0 to SSP5-8.5 are provided with calibrated emulator.

More and more emulators of this kind should be developed and calibrated for rapid and less expensive way of exploring tipping points. Therefore, this study is important and relevant.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: I am expert of large scale climate dynamics including AMOC dynamics, however I lack mathematical expertise to evaluate emulator design and concepts. I request editor please provide extra weightage to other reviewers comment before making decision.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Reviewer Report 16 June 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.21075.r54758>

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Valerian Jacques-Dumas

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Short summary

This article presents a simple tipping elements and tipping cascades emulator, which can be tuned to the dynamics of more complex models. The authors model the tipping behaviour of the AMOC and GIS as coupled double-fold bifurcations and tune their parameters to independent hysteresis experiments in the cGENIE model. The methodology for tuning these parameters already existed but was limited to a single forcing variable. The authors extended it to an arbitrary number of forcing variables and show that they are able to reasonably reproduce the dynamics of cGENIE. This simple emulator is then coupled to SURFER, where it is used to explore the response of the AMOC to a large range of SSP scenarios. This approach allows the derivation of the critical manifold in the forcing space; the inclusion of multiple forcings also shows new overshoot and tipping trajectories that could not be observed before.

Review summary: Approved with reservations

Tackling the issue of computational cost is very important to study tipping cascades and, more generally, tipping elements. Using simple emulators tuned to complex dynamics is an appealing way to solve this problem so I find the overall method, the results and perspectives of this study to be interesting and worth publishing. However, I have some comments and general remarks that should be addressed to enhance readability and reproducibility.

Major comments

1) My major concern is the readability of the article. Many sentences are confusing and I had to read them multiple times before understanding. Moreover, some grammatical mistakes also hinder readability. Some examples are given below but I would suggest to read again through the article carefully.

- (Section 1.3) "However, the AMOC is influenced by two forcing variables: temperature anomaly and freshwater flux. Given the necessity of more realistically constraining potential future AMOC trajectories, this study seeks to address the following objective: develop an

AMOC emulator with two forcing parameters — temperature and freshwater flux — that can be calibrated against hysteresis from complex models and integrated into a climate model.”

This is redundant and overly complicated. “However” at the beginning is also wrongly used, leading to some confusion.

- (Section 2.2) “Mathematically, the generalization to N forcing variables results in obtaining $4N - 2(N - 1)$ equations with $4 + (N - 1)$ knowns, leading to $N - 1$ over-determined equations. As will be shown in the next section with the emulation of cGENIE, these over-determinations reflect the fact that the coefficient c_1 is the shared constant across all calibrations of different sensitivity experiments. It represents the component of the model that must adjust for each sensitivity experiment while remaining consistent across all of them.”

This could be made simpler and clearer.

- (Section 2.2) “For instance, the simulation, with a forcing duration of 2000 years to reach equilibrium, can start with a 0 Sv forcing. It then increases the forcing by 0.05 Sv to slow down the AMOC, decreases the forcing by 0.05 Sv until the value reaches -0.05 Sv, and repeats this procedure several times. The goal is to obtain a time series of the AMOC intensity with several instances where the AMOC is being reduced.”

This is VERY confusing. It took me several attempts to understand it and I thought it would be a linear ramping-up so Figure 3b came as a surprise. It could be rephrased more simply and more efficiently.

- (Section 3.1) “Nevertheless, they do not compromise the calibration of the parameter τ , as it is designed to replicate the temporal lag between the AMOC intensity at a given moment and its corresponding equilibrium intensity during the four forcing level transitions in EXPC.”

The end of this sentence is unclear.

- (Section 3.1) “The goal is to calibrate the parameter τ to reproduce the time lag between the intensity of the AMOC and its corresponding equilibrium intensity under the applied forcing.”

This sentence is unclear, partly because of the expression “intensity of the AMOC”

- (Section 4) “While it is highly likely that the model values deviate from exact accuracy, we demonstrate that they are sufficiently well calibrated to remain plausible.”

This sentence is very unclear, especially in relation with the previous sentence. What do you mean here? Could you rephrase it?

2) Across the article, authors mention that hysteresis are performed on a single forcing parameter while keeping the other fixed at certain value T^B or F_{GIS}^A . However, what precise values are given other than these variables are never explicit in the Results section. This must be important, though for the calibration of the ATCM. Can you make it clearer? Figure 2 suggests that these extra parameters are fixed to 0 but it should be in the text. After re-reading, I understood that the fixed values are the ones presented in Table 1, is it correct? If so, it should be made clearer in the text.

3) Moreover, Figure 2 is not very clear. You could consider making it 2 panels, one for each variable.

4) Similarly, I would strongly encourage you to replace Figure S4 with two panels because the bifurcation points in the intertwined planes are not readable at all. In particular, I cannot check from the Figure that the values of T - and F_{GIS} you mention are the right ones.

5) The other important point is the generalisation of your results. You claim that their emulator is very flexible in reproducing tipping behaviour, which is very appealing, but validate it using the same parameters as for calibration. As far as I understand, the experiment `val_exp_1` simply combines the parameter ramp-ups of EXPA and EXPB. It would be very interesting to see how the emulator performs when validated (against cGENIE) for different hosing experiments and global warming scenarios. This would also support the interesting dynamics observed when the emulator is applied to a whole range of SSP scenarios.

6) In the Supplementary Material S1, you go through the whole calibration procedure for the GIS but do not present any result. I find it a pity that you show the whole method to potentially simulate AMOC-GIS tipping interaction, but stop there. Could you consider adding these results to the paper (if there is enough room)? Otherwise, is it worth keeping this Section of the Supplementary Material? If the AMOC-GIS interaction results are out of the scope of this paper, I think that the calibration of the GIS model is also out of its scope.

7) In relation with this point, at the very end of Section 2.1, you write "In the results section, we calibrate $\tau + \Psi$ and $\tau - \Psi$ based on a tuning procedure to reproduce the internal timescale dynamics of the AMOC in cGENIE. For the GIS, we set $V + \tau = 5500$ years and $V - \tau = 700$ years, based on reasonable values given in the reviews by Armstrong McKay et al.[29] and Couplet et al.[40]."

- Why mention the time scales of the GIS if you do not use them at all afterwards? And if you use them later, you should rather give at the same place where you explain the calibration of AMOC time scales (end of Section 2.2).

7) (Section 3.1) "Since the primary objective of the ATCM is to accurately calibrate the collapse branch, we focus exclusively on simulating collapse scenarios with cGENIE."

- You describe the whole procedure to calibrate all parameters of your emulator (including the return time scale τ_{minus}) and even provide in Supplementary Material (Section S4) the full hysteresis experiments which would allow you to perform the whole calibration. Why not use it? Wouldn't it make your results more robust by bringing additional constraint?

8) (Section 4) "Moreover, the emulator allows assessing, under the assumption that the two forcings add linearly, the critical manifold W_c of the emulated complex model."

- Could you discuss this assumption? Is it a strong assumption? Has it already been discussed elsewhere?

9) (Conclusion) Most of your Conclusion is redundant with your Discussion. Can you consider removing the conclusion and slightly expanding the discussion to avoid repeating the same things twice?

10) (Supplementary Material, Section 1). I don't understand this section. Is it even possible in cGENIE to increase the temperature while keeping the AMOC strength constant? It seems very strange since you also claim that the P-E anomaly stemming from global warming is the main driver of AMOC weakening. Moreover, you never mention what is the fixed value of the AMOC strength. Similarly, when you vary the AMOC strength (how? Is it a model parameter?), you fix the global mean temperature but don't explicitly give the value of $T_{\text{V}^{\text{D}}}$. You can leave most details in the MSc thesis you cite but everything needed for reproduction of your results should be in the

article.

11) In relation with this comment, the sentence "For the GIS case, it requires a complex model capable of simulating its volume projections with independent forcing possibilities for the AMOC and temperature." in Section 2.2 is not very clear.

12)

- (Section 3.1) "However, to achieve an optimal fit for the collapse trajectory, slight deviations from the bifurcation point coordinates provided by the complex model may improve the emulator's accuracy in representing the collapse trajectory."
- (Caption of Table 1) "The T- value was adjusted to improve the calibration of the upper branch."
- (Supplementary Material, Section 4) "Additionally, to improve the calibration of the emulator on the collapse branch, it was shown in Laridon (52) that arbitrarily changing the coordinates of the second bifurcation point improves calibration. For this reason, in this study, we reuse the critical values of the second bifurcation point from these two experiments to focus on longer calibration runs that more effectively capture the AMOC collapse at the first bifurcation point, given that forcing can act more slowly in the calibration experiments described in the main text."

What does it mean that you "adjust" or "arbitrarily change" the value of T- to improve calibration? Moreover, I do not really understand the sentences quoted here from the Supplementary Material: they are very heavy and not clear at all.

Minor comments

1) (Section 1.2) "However, due to their prohibitive computational demands, complex models, such as Earth System Models (ESMs) are unable to simulate numerous complete AMOC hysteresis curves[36]."

- You already cite van Westen et. al (2024) but not here unfortunately. It would be particularly relevant because they precisely compute a hysteresis curve from an ESM.

2) (Section 2.1) "In Equation (1), this term encapsulates the physical effects of warming on AMOC water stratification, as well as freshwater anomalies resulting from simulated P-E in the complex model."

- This is confusing because it seems that T represents at the same time temperature and salinity. Moreover, after that, you no longer mention its P-E component. You could thus simplify this sentence and leave the whole P-E flux to the Supplementary Materials.

3) (Section 2.2) "Based on Armstrong McKay et al.²⁹ we assume that the internal dynamic time scale of the AMOC from its nominal stable state to its collapse stable state is the same, i.e., $\Psi \tau_{-} + \Psi \tau_{+} \equiv \tau$ "

- Has this actually been checked in sensitivity experiments?

4) (Section 3.1, paragraph 3) Don't you mean EXPB instead of EXPA?

5) (Section 3.1, paragraph 3) "The freshwater hosing is applied between 20°N and 50°N across the full width of the Atlantic (Figure S3- See underlying data) to reproduce the hosing region by Rahmstorf et al.[27]."

- Could you comment on the influence of this choice? Different hosing areas have since then been compared, for instance in [1].

6) (Section 3.2) "However, after 3,000 years, a sudden drop in AMOC intensity, followed by a partial recovery, is not captured by the ATCM."

- Do you know why such drop happens? Had it already been observed?

7) (Section 3.4) "As an application, we studied the response of the ATCM once integrated into SURFER under 15 different emission scenarios spanning SSP1-2.6 to SSP5-8.5."

- Do you have any references on the design of these scenarios?

8) At the end of Section 3.3 and in Section 3.4, you reference Figure 5 twice, although it should be Figure 6.

9) (Supplementary Material, Section 1) "We denote $\diamond\diamond\diamond\diamond\diamond\diamond\diamond$, in the case of the GIS as the first calibration experiment of the GIS volume in relation to temperature."

- This sentence should be rephrased for clarity.

10) (Supplementary Material, section 2) "The duration of $\diamond\diamond\diamond\diamond\diamond\diamond\diamond$ was choose to"

- The verb should be "chosen".

11) (Supplementary Material, Section 4) "For $\diamond\diamond\diamond\diamond\diamond\diamond\diamond$, it was also a 20,000-year run,"

- This is not consistent with the beginning with the rest of the paragraph. From what I understand from the end of the paragraph, the full EXPB run lasts 20,000 years. But the EXPA run lasts 40,000 years. So in the sentence quoted here, you cannot use "also" and "20,000 years" together, otherwise it's very confusing. In this same sentence, "-0.2 Sv" is cut, with "-" on one line and "0.2 Sv" on the next, although they should stay together for clarity.

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Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.**Reviewer Expertise:** Extreme and rare events, AMOC, nonlinear dynamics, machine learning**I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.**

Author Response 17 Oct 2025

Amaury Laridon**Major comments**

1) Readability of the article *"My major concern is the readability of the article. Many sentences are confusing and I had to read them multiple times before understanding. Moreover, some grammatical mistakes also hinder readability. Some examples are given below but I would suggest to read again through the article carefully."* Thank you for raising this concern. We have carefully reviewed the entire manuscript and reformulated numerous sentences to enhance clarity and readability. Special attention was devoted to all highlighted sections, which have been systematically revised.

2) Clear mention of the value of the constant forcing parameter *"Across the article, authors mention that hysteresis are performed on a single forcing parameter while keeping the other fixed at certain value T^A or F_{GIS}^A . However, what precise values are given other than these variables are never explicit in the Results section. This must be important, though for the calibration of the ATCM. Can you make it clearer? Figure 2 suggests that these extra parameters are fixed to 0 but it should be in the text. After re-reading, I understood that the fixed values are the ones presented in Table 1, is it correct? If so, it should be made clearer in the text."* Indeed, it was an oversight that these fixed values were not specified in the Results section nor discussed further in the Discussion. We have now addressed this by explicitly stating the values chosen for F_{GIS}^A and T^A in the Results section and by including them in Table 1. In the Discussion section, we have added a paragraph presenting the scientific rationale behind our choice of setting $F_{GIS}^A=0$ Sv and $T^A=0$ °C, as well as the implications of using alternative fixed but non-zero values for these two parameters.

3) Figure 2 not very clear *"Figure 2 is not very clear. You could consider making it 2 panels, one for each variable."* We appreciate the reviewer's suggestion. However, we would prefer to keep Figure 2 in its current form, as we believe that presenting the full forcing space in a single panel effectively conveys the range of possible combinations between temperature and freshwater flux. This unified representation is intended to emphasize that only two calibration experiments are sufficient to approximate the complex system dynamics within the entire forcing space. The specific values of the coordinates corresponding to the bifurcation points identified in the figure are provided in Table 1 for clarity. Following the reviewer's comment, we have added a sentence in the manuscript, when introducing this

figure, to further highlight its purpose of providing a visual representation of the now two-dimensional forcing space. This addition further supports our argument that the emulator will subsequently enable sampling across this wide parameter space. Finally, we have included in the Supplementary Materials the two 2D plots of the bifurcation diagrams for temperature and freshwater forcing alone, in order to enhance readability.

4) Figure S4 not very clear and values used for T-and FGIS- *Similarly, I would strongly encourage you to replace Figure S4 with two panels because the bifurcation points in the intertwined planes are not readable at all. In particular, I cannot check from the Figure that the values of T- and F_GIS you mention are the right ones.* Thank you for raising this concern. We have ultimately decided to remove Section 4 from the Supplementary Materials. The main reason is that this section contained an error and did not contribute to the clarity of the presentation; on the contrary, it was confusing. Specifically, the values chosen for T and FGIS- are not directly those from the simulation results presented in A. Laridon's MSc thesis. As previously stated—though perhaps not clearly enough—these values were artificially modified in the emulator, based on the rationale that the focus of this study is to demonstrate that a good calibration on the collapse branch, which is of greater near-term interest, can be achieved. It is also now reminded in Section 3.1 that there is a trade-off in calibrating the emulator to minimize the calibration error where it is most relevant given the scientific objective. Section 4 was originally included to show that it is also possible to calibrate the emulator on a full hysteresis curve, but its presentation and the way it was referenced in Section 3.1 were confusing. We have therefore rewritten the explanation of the choices and justifications for the values of T and FGIS- , while inviting readers interested in the full hysteresis calibration results to consult the MSc thesis.

5) Generalization of the results *The other important point is the generalisation of your results. You claim that their emulator is very flexible in reproducing tipping behaviour, which is very appealing, but validate it using the same parameters as for calibration. As far as I understand, the experiment val_exp_1 simply combines the parameter ramp-ups of EXPA and EXPB. It would be very interesting to see how the emulator performs when validated (against cGENIE) for different hosing experiments and global warming scenarios. This would also support the interesting dynamics observed when the emulator is applied to a whole range of SSP scenarios.* We thank the reviewer for this very relevant and constructive suggestion. In response, we now validate the emulator against four new scenarios in the revised manuscript: SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5, each with and without an added hosing flux of 0.06 Sv. We provide a more detailed description of the experimental protocol in the updated manuscript. In addition, we performed a new calibration experiment for the timescale-related parameter, which allows a strict separation between the experiments used for calibration and those used for validation. We believe that these additions further reinforce the conclusions already presented in the previous version of the study.

6) Method developed for AMOC-GIS tipping interaction but not used *In the Supplementary Material S1, you go through the whole calibration procedure for the GIS but do not present any result. I find it a pity that you show the whole method to potentially simulate AMOC-GIS tipping interaction, but stop there. Could you consider adding these results to the paper (if there is enough room)? Otherwise, is it worth keeping this Section of the Supplementary Material? If the AMOC-GIS interaction results are out of the scope of this paper, I think that the*

calibration of the GIS model is also out of its scope. We thank the reviewer for this thoughtful comment. In the revised manuscript, we have modified Figure 1 by removing the GIS equation, as it unnecessarily complicated the interpretation of the figure. This change also makes the parameter τ more explicit. In addition, we have moved the former Equation (2), which described the evolution of the GIS, from the Methods section to Subsection 3.3 of the Results, where we integrate the emulator into SURFER. Finally, we have removed the previous parameterization of the AMOC to GIS interaction, as it was partly arbitrary and based on the MSc thesis of A. Laridon. We now adopt exactly the same equation and calibration as in SURFER v2.0 (Martinez Monteiro et al., (2022)), ensuring greater consistency, transparency, and reproducibility in our results. The primary objective of this study was to demonstrate the feasibility of constructing a two-variable forcing emulator capable of reproducing consistent results when compared with a target complex model. We have included Section S1 in the Supplementary Materials to illustrate how the proposed mathematical framework can also be applied to the construction and calibration of a GIS emulator, thereby enabling the exploration of potential tipping cascades between the AMOC and the GIS. While some example applications of this methodology are presented in the MSc thesis of A. Laridon, we have not yet calibrated the simplified GIS model against a complex GIS model. The purpose of Section S1 is therefore to outline the theoretical and methodological groundwork for such an extension, rather than to present calibrated results. Given the focus of the present paper, a full calibration of the GIS model and a detailed analysis of potential AMOC–GIS interactions are beyond its scope. However, we agree that these represent promising avenues for future research. We have clarified this motivation and limitation in the revised manuscript to better reflect the role of Section S1, in addition to the modifications described above.

7) Choice of the $\tau_{V\pm}$ *In relation with this point, at the very end of Section 2.1, you write “In the results section, we calibrate $\tau + \Psi$ and $\tau - \Psi$ based on a tuning procedure to reproduce the internal timescale dynamics of the AMOC in cGENIE. For the GIS, we set $V + \tau = 5500$ years and $V - \tau = 700$ years, based on reasonable values given in the reviews by Armstrong McKay et al.[29] and Couplet et al.[40].” Why mention the time scales of the GIS if you do not use them at all afterwards? And if you use them later, you should rather give at the same place where you explain the calibration of AMOC time scales (end if Section 2.2).* We thank the reviewer for pointing out this lack of clarity. We have now added the missing information regarding the values of τ_{V+} et τ_{V-} in section 3.3. As mentioned in the previous comment, we now use exactly the same equation to describe the dynamics of the GIS, as well as the calibration parameters, as in SURFER v2.0 (cfr. Martinez Monteiro et al.(2022)). In that paper, the GIS equation was calibrated against the results of a complex GIS model. By adopting exactly the same GIS equation here, we are also able to compare the emulator’s results—with and without freshwater flux forcing—more rigorously than in the first version of the manuscript.

8) Assumption that the two forcings add linearly (Section 4) *“Moreover, the emulator allows assessing, under the assumption that the two forcings add linearly, the critical manifold W_c of the emulated complex model.” Could you discuss this assumption? Is it a strong assumption? Has it already been discussed elsewhere?* Assuming that the forcings combine linearly is a common methodological choice, largely because it offers a straightforward and tractable starting point. While there is no definitive evidence that this assumption strictly holds, the fact that

few tipping experiments in complex models consider multiple forcings makes it challenging to adopt an alternative approach. The aim of the emulator is therefore to provide a tool that, under the most common and simplified assumption of treating the two dominant AMOC forcings linearly, enables an assessment of AMOC sensitivity across different complex models. As discussed further in the revised manuscript, adopting alternative values for *FGISA* and *TB* would make it possible to test the robustness of the assumption that the two forcings add linearly. However, if future literature supports a new prevailing hypothesis regarding the analytical form of the combination of these two forcings, it would be entirely possible to reformulate the AMOC equation in the emulator and apply the same calibration method to it.

9) Repetitions between the Conclusions and the Discussions (*Conclusion*) *Most of your Conclusion is redundant with your Discussion. Can you consider removing the conclusion and slightly expanding the discussion to avoid repeating the same things twice?* We acknowledge the reviewer's comment regarding the perceived redundancy between the conclusion and the discussion sections. In response, we have expanded the discussion to include additional points, making it more comprehensive and revised the conclusion.

10) Supplementary Materials, Section 1 – More clear information for reproduction *I don't understand this section. Is it even possible in cGENIE to increase the temperature while keeping the AMOC strength constant? It seems very strange since you also claim that the P-E anomaly stemming from global warming is the main driver of AMOC weakening. Moreover, you never mention what is the fixed value of the AMOC strength. Similarly, when you vary the AMOC strength (how? Is it a model parameter?), you fix the global mean temperature but don't explicitly give the value of T_V^D . You can leave most details in the MSc thesis you cite but everything needed for reproduction of your results should be in the article.* The purpose of Section 1 of the Supplementary Materials is purely to provide a technical demonstration of how the same calibration method can be applied to a simplified model of the GIS in order to construct an emulator. We have added a paragraph at the beginning of this section to clarify its objective and to emphasize that applying this framework requires the availability of a complex model of the GIS. cGENIE, in itself, is not capable of producing the two calibration experiments required to emulate the GIS, assuming its two main forcings are global mean atmospheric temperature anomaly and AMOC intensity. Indeed, cGENIE does not include an explicit representation of the GIS or its melt processes. In this section, we describe in the protocol of *EXPC* that, using a suitable complex GIS model, a first sensitivity experiment should be conducted in which the GIS is forced by the atmospheric temperature anomaly while keeping AMOC intensity fixed. Using the notation of the section, the value is denoted as $\Psi_V = \Psi_V^C$. Similarly, for the second calibration experiment *EXPD*, the atmospheric temperature anomaly is held constant at a generic value $T_V = T_V^D$. It is expected that these numerical values are not provided, as these simulations have not been conducted. Once again, the sole purpose of this section is to present the mathematical framework and to highlight the operational constraints that such an application would impose on the complex GIS model to be used. We have also revised the citation of the MSc Thesis to make it clearer to the reader what can be expected from it. In the MSc Thesis, the GIS model was not calibrated based on a complex GIS model either; instead, parameter values were chosen based on reasonable assumptions drawn from the literature (e.g., Armstrong McKay et al. (2022)). However, the work did investigate the coupled emulator framework between the AMOC and GIS, and the

potential tipping dynamics of both systems.

11) Section 2.2 – Need of a complex model for the GIS *In relation with this comment, the sentence “For the GIS case, it requires a complex model capable of simulating its volume projections with independent forcing possibilities for the AMOC and temperature.” in Section 2.2 is not very clear. As explained in our response to comment number 6, we have now relocated and revised the presentation of the GIS dynamics used in the manuscript. It is now strictly based on that of SURFER v2.0, which has already been published and was calibrated against a complex GIS model.*

12) Arbitrarily change the value of T- *(Section 3.1) “However, to achieve an optimal fit for the collapse trajectory, slight deviations from the bifurcation point coordinates provided by the complex model may improve the emulator’s accuracy in representing the collapse trajectory.”* ○ (Caption of Table 1) “The T- value was adjusted to improve the calibration of the upper branch.” ○ (Supplementary Material, Section 4) “Additionally, to improve the calibration of the emulator on the collapse branch, it was shown in Laridon (52) that arbitrarily changing the coordinates of the second bifurcation point improves calibration. For this reason, in this study, we reuse the critical values of the second bifurcation point from these two experiments to focus on longer calibration runs that more effectively capture the AMOC collapse at the first bifurcation point, given that forcing can act more slowly in the calibration experiments described in the main text.” ○ What does it mean that you “adjust” or “arbitrarily change” the value of T- to improve calibration? Moreover, I do not really understand the sentences quoted here from the Supplementary Material: they are very heavy and not clear at all. As previously stated, we have decided to remove Section 4 of the Supplementary Materials, as it did not contribute to improving the clarity of the manuscript. As mentioned in response to Point (4) above, we have also revised Section 3.1 to clarify which bifurcation point coordinates are derived from the two cGENIE sensitivity experiments that are shown, and which coordinates are manually fixed to improve the calibration of the upper collapse branch. We now provide a clearer justification for this choice in Section 3.1. Accordingly, for the parameters Ψ -, $FGIS$ -, T -, we have also updated the description of Table 1 to make it explicit that these values are manually set.

Minor comments

1) Nuance on van Westen et al.(2024) citation *(Section 1.2) “However, due to their prohibitive computational demands, complex models, such as Earth System Models (ESMs) are unable to simulate numerous complete AMOC hysteresis curves[36].” You already cite van Westen et. al (2024) but not here unfortunately. It would be particularly relevant because they precisely compute a hysteresis curve from an ESM. We have added a reference to the study by van Westen et al. (2024) in this part of Section 1.2, emphasising that although hysteresis curves from ESMs do now exist, they remain scarce due to the high computational cost associated with producing them.*

2) P-E mention in the T-forcing *(Section 2.1) “In Equation (1), this term encapsulates the physical effects of warming on AMOC water stratification, as well as freshwater anomalies resulting from simulated P-E in the complex model.” This is confusing because it seems that T represents at the same time temperature and salinity. Moreover, after that, you no longer mention its P-E component. You could thus simplify this sentence and leave the whole P-E flux to*

the Supplementary Materials. This has been addressed by removing the statement in Section 2.1 suggesting that the variable T accounts not only for the effect of heat on stratification but also for freshwater anomalies related to precipitation-minus-evaporation (P–E). That statement was indeed confusing. However, the explanation that the effect of P–E can be captured if it is also simulated by the complex model has been retained in Section 3.1. In this order, we believe the reading is much clearer.

3) Verification of $\tau_+ = \tau_-$ in sensitivity experiments (Section 2.2) *“Based on Armstrong McKay et al.²⁹ we assume that the internal dynamic time scale of the AMOC from its nominal stable state to its collapse stable state is the same, i.e., $\tau_{\Psi^-} = \tau_{\Psi^+}$ ”* ○ Has this actually been checked in sensitivity experiments? These two parameters by themselves do not represent the total time required for the AMOC to tip from its ON state to its OFF state and vice versa, but rather characterize the internal dynamic time scales associated with the AMOC’s strengthening and weakening phases. Based on the analysis presented in Gérard and Crucifix (2024)¹, Figures 7a and 7b illustrate hysteresis loops of AMOC intensity in response to atmospheric temperature anomalies and freshwater flux forcing. From these figures, we observe that, to a first approximation, the system spends a comparable amount of time transitioning from the ON to the OFF state as it does from the OFF to the ON state. Specifically, in both cases, the transition appears to take approximately 2000 years, which supports our assumption that $\tau_{\Psi^+} = \tau_{\Psi^-}$.

¹ Gérard J, Crucifix M. Diagnosing the causes of AMOC slowdown in a coupled model: a cautionary tale. *Earth System Dynamics*. 2024 Mar 22;15(2):293–306.

4) Typo (Section 3.1, paragraph 3) *Don’t you mean EXPB instead of EXPA?* Yes, indeed — thank you for pointing this out. We have corrected it accordingly.

5) Choice of the hosing region (Section 3.1, paragraph 3) *“The freshwater hosing is applied between 20°N and 50°N across the full width of the Atlantic (Figure S3- See underlying data) to reproduce the hosing region by Rahmstorf et al.[27].”* Could you comment on the influence of this choice? Different hosing areas have since then been compared, for instance in [1]. We selected this region to apply the hosing in cGENIE because it is the one used in previous hosing experiments with the same model (see Rahmstorf et al. (2005)² and Gérard and Crucifix (2025)). The rationale behind choosing this specific latitude band was to deliberately avoid deep convection regions, in order not to shut down the AMOC too abruptly. Furthermore, Laridon (2024)³ has shown that the differences between this latitude band and a higher one, such as 50°N–70°N, are not significant, given that cGENIE is not a high-resolution model. What matters most when selecting the hosing region in the Atlantic is the consistency of its location across the different complex models that we aim to emulate. This ensures that no indirect bias is introduced in the subsequent calibration and comparison of the AMOC emulator versions.

² Rahmstorf S, Crucifix M, Ganopolski A, Goosse H, Kamenkovich I, Knutti R, et al. Thermohaline circulation hysteresis: A model intercomparison. *Geophysical Research Letters* [Internet]. 2005 [cited 2023 Oct 22];32(23). Available from:

<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1029/2005GL023655>

³ Laridon Amaury. Development of a Simplified Dynamics Emulator and Investigation of Cascading Collapses of the AMOC and Greenland Ice Sheet in a Climate Model [Internet]. UCLouvain; 2024. Available from:

<https://dial.uclouvain.be/memoire/ucl/object/thesis:46552>

6) Drop in the AMOC intensity after 3000 years (Section 3.2) *“However, after 3,000 years, a sudden drop in AMOC intensity, followed by a partial recovery, is not captured by the ATCM.”* ○ Do you know why such drop happens? Had it already been observed? J. Gérard, one of the co-authors of this paper and the researcher who conducted the cGENIE simulations, has substantial expertise with this model, which he also employs in his own research. According to his interpretation, the abrupt decrease observed likely corresponds to the AMOC entering the self-sustained oscillatory regime that exists in cGENIE, as previously described in Gérard and Crucifix (2024) 1 (see Figure 7a). However, in our setup, the AMOC is forced not only by atmospheric temperature anomalies but also by freshwater fluxes, which further limits the time the system remains within this limit cycle. As a result, the system exits the cycle rapidly, preventing a full oscillation from becoming apparent. This behaviour is therefore understood to be specific to the cGENIE model.

1 Gérard J, Crucifix M. Diagnosing the causes of AMOC slowdown in a coupled model: a cautionary tale. *Earth System Dynamics*. 2024 Mar 22;15(2):293–306.

7) References of the design of the emissions scenarios ? (Section 3.4) *“As an application, we studied the response of the ATCM once integrated into SURFER under 15 different emission scenarios spanning SSP1-2.6 to SSP5-8.5.”* ○ Do you have any references on the design of these scenarios? Indeed, we had not specified the references for these scenarios. The reader can find them in Appendix A.2 of V. Couplet’s PhD thesis. We have now added the corresponding details in the manuscript, as well as in the “Data Availability” section.

8) Typo of references in Figure 5 *At the end of Section 3.3 and in Section 3.4, you reference Figure 5 twice, although it should be Figure 6.* Yes, indeed — thank you for pointing this out. We have corrected it accordingly.

9) Typo in Supplementary Materials (Supplementary Material, Section 1) *“We denote *

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.
